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The water footprint of agricultural products in European river basins

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Abstract

This work quantifies the agricultural water footprint (WF) of production ($WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$) and consumption ($WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$) and the resulting net virtual water import ($\text{netVW}_{i, \text{agr}}$) of 365 European river basins for a reference period (REF, 1996–2005) and two diet scenarios (a healthy diet based upon food-based dietary guidelines (HEALTHY) and a vegetarian (VEG) diet). In addition to total (tot) amounts, a differentiation is also made between the green (gn), blue (bl) and grey (gy) components. River basins where the REF $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ exceeds the $WF_{\text{prod, agr, tot}}$ (resulting in positive $\text{netVW}_{i, \text{agr, tot}}$ values), are found along the London–Milan axis. These include the Thames, Scheldt, Meuse, Seine, Rhine and Po basins. River basins where the $WF_{\text{prod, agr, tot}}$ exceeds the $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ are found in Western France, the Iberian Peninsula and the Baltic region. These include the Loire, Ebro and Nemunas basins. Under the HEALTHY diet scenario, the $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ of most river basins decreases (max -32%), although it was found to increase in some basins in northern and eastern Europe. This results in 22 river basins, including the Danube, shifting from being net VW importers to being net VW exporters. A reduction (max -46%) in $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ is observed for all but one river basin under the VEG diet scenario. In total, 50 river basins shift from being net VW importers to being net exporters, including the Danube, Seine, Rhone and Elbe basins. Similar observations are made when only the gn + bl and gn components are assessed. When analysing only the bl component, a different river basin pattern is observed.

 Online supplementary data available from stacks.iop.org/ERL/9/064007/mmedia

Keywords: water footprint, EU, river basin, diet, indicator, sustainability, virtual water

1. Introduction

The water footprint (WF, table 1) concept has been brought into water management science in order to show the importance of consumption patterns and the global dimensions in good water governance (Galli *et al* 2012, Hoekstra and Mekonnen 2012, Vanham and Bidoglio 2013a). It is an indicator of direct and indirect water use. An assessment of the WF of all nations has recently been conducted by Hoekstra and Mekonnen (2012). It is important to distinguish

between the WF of production (WF_{prod}) and the WF of consumption (WF_{cons}) of a geographical region. The first refers to the total use of domestic water resources within the region (for producing goods and services for either domestic consumption or for export). The second refers to the use of domestic and foreign water resources behind all goods and services that are consumed domestically. A balance between the two is reached by virtual water (VW) flows (imports (VW_i) and exports (VW_e)), and more particularly by the netVW_i (VW_i minus VW_e), which equals WF_{cons} minus WF_{prod} . WFs consist of blue, green and grey components. Following the definition of Rockström *et al* (2009), green water is the soil water held in the unsaturated zone, formed by precipitation and available to plants, while blue water refers to liquid water in rivers, lakes, wetlands and aquifers. Irrigated

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Figure 1 River basins (size larger than 1000 km²) that are located (partly) in the EU and remaining Balkan countries for which the assessment was carried out. The names of major basins are depicted.

agriculture receives blue water (from irrigation) as well as green water (from precipitation), while rainfed agriculture only receives green water. The green WF is thus the rainwater consumed by crops. The grey WF is an indicator of the degree of water pollution (Hoekstra *et al* 2011).

This paper conducts the following analyses for the river basins (partly) located in the EU and remaining Balkan countries (basin size larger than 1000 km²) (figure 1): the reference (REF) WF of production for agricultural products ($WF_{prod, agr}$), the reference WF of consumption for agricultural products ($WF_{cons, agr}$) and the resulting reference net VW import for agricultural products ($netVW_{i, agr}$). Additionally the $WF_{cons, agr}$ for two diet scenarios is analysed: a healthy diet (HEALTHY) and a vegetarian diet (VEG). The resulting change in $netVW_{i, agr}$ is also assessed for all river basins. All these analyses are carried out for the total WF ($WF_{prod, agr, tot}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot}$), the green WF ($WF_{prod, agr, gn}$, $WF_{cons, agr, gn}$, $netVW_{i, agr, gn}$), the blue WF ($WF_{prod, agr, bl}$, $WF_{cons, agr, bl}$, $netVW_{i, agr, bl}$) and the green plus blue WF ($WF_{prod, agr, gn+bl}$, $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$, $netVW_{i, agr, gn+bl}$).

To date, the $WF_{prod, agr}$ has been assessed for some selected large river basins (Aldaya and Llamas 2009, Dumont *et al* 2013, Zeng *et al* 2012, Zhao *et al* 2010, Hoekstra *et al* 2012), but not covering the whole EU like in this study. The $WF_{cons, agr}$ has only been assessed in the literature on a national basis but not for river basins. The $netVW_{i, agr, tot}$ has been analysed in Vanham (2013a) for EU river basins. However, the author acknowledges that for policy options there is a need to compute the different components (green, blue and grey), which was not done in that study. The effect of diets on the WF_{cons} has been carried out for the city of

Table 1 Abbreviations used in the letter.

Abbreviation	Definition
WF	water footprint
WF_{prod}	water footprint of production
WF_{cons}	water footprint of consumption
$WF_{prod, agr}$	agricultural water footprint of production
$WF_{prod-crops, agr}$	agricultural water footprint of production for crops
$WF_{prod-liv, agr}$	agricultural water footprint of production for livestock
$WF_{cons, agr}$	agricultural water footprint of consumption
gn	green
bl	blue
gy	grey
gn + bl	green + blue
tot	total
$WF_{prod, agr, gn}$; $WF_{prod, agr, bl}$; $WF_{prod, agr, gy}$; $WF_{prod, agr, gn+bl}$ and $WF_{prod, agr, tot}$	green; blue; grey; green + blue respectively total agricultural water footprint of production
$WF_{cons, agr, gn}$; $WF_{cons, agr, bl}$; $WF_{cons, agr, gy}$; $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$ and $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$	green; blue; grey; green + blue respectively total agricultural water footprint of consumption
VW	virtual water
VW_i/VW_e	virtual water import/export
$VW_{i, agr}/VW_{e, agr}$	agricultural virtual water import/export
$netVW_i/netVW_e$	net VW import/export
$netVW_{i, agr}/netVW_{e, agr}$	agricultural net VW import/export
REF	reference period (1996–2005)
FBDG	Food-Based Dietary Guidelines
HEALTHY	healthy diet
VEG	vegetarian diet
DGE	German nutrition society (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ernährung)
NORTH	Northern diet
MED	Mediterranean diet
GLW	gridded livestock of the world

Milan (Vanham and Bidoglio 2014), China (Liu and Save-nije 2008), Austria (Vanham 2013b), the EU as a whole (Vanham *et al* 2013b) and for four EU zones (Vanham *et al* 2013a). In the latter study, the importance of a regional analysis is stressed. The effect of different diets on the $WF_{cons, agr}$ (and the resulting change in $netVW_{i, agr}$) of a river basin has not been carried out to date. River basins, not administrative borders, are the key geographical entities for water management. The main instrument for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive is the River Basin Management Plan (EC 2012). This study presents a first comprehensive agricultural WF accounting analysis of 365 European river basins, including the effect of various diet scenarios.

Figure 2 Workflow of the methodology used in the paper.

Indeed, in the framework of the global water-food-energy-ecosystem nexus, the analysis conducted in this paper gives essential information.

2. Methodology

2.1. General

The methodology to compute $WF_{prod, agr}$ and $WF_{cons, agr}$ (and resulting $netVW_{i, agr}$) river basin values based upon national values (as obtained from Hoekstra and Mekonnen (2012a)) and a $WF_{prod, agr}$ geodataset for crops ($WF_{prod, agr-crops}$) is presented in figure 2. To assess the effect of the two diets (HEALTHY and VEG) on the national $WF_{cons, agr}$, the approach of Vanham *et al* (2013a) is applied. The most detailed geographical level for such an analysis is the national level, due to data restrictions. In this paper such an analysis is conducted for each of the 40 nations separately—based upon regional Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDG) for HEALTHY as presented in table A.1—and results then transposed to river basin level. To date, such a detailed national assessment with respect to these 40 nations has only been conducted for Austria (Vanham 2013b). For the VEG, all meat of the healthy diet is substituted by an increase in the intake of products from the group pulses, nuts and oilcrops with equal caloric value and protein content.

2.2. River basins

The catchment database for continental Europe (CCM2), developed by Vogt *et al* (2007) (based on the digital elevation model SRTM—Shuttle Radar Topography Mission—of 90 m resolution), was used to identify the river basins (figure 1). Selected basins have to fulfil two conditions: (1) they are fully or partly located in the EU28 and remaining Balkan countries; (2) they have a surface area larger than 1000 km².

2.3. Accounting framework

We follow the Global Water Footprint Standard developed by the Water Footprint Network (Hoekstra *et al* 2011). National data on the green, blue and grey $WF_{cons, agr}$ for each nation are obtained from Hoekstra and Mekonnen (2012) and Mekonnen and Hoekstra (2011b). The WF_{cons} of agricultural products is calculated with the bottom-up approach, based upon direct underlying national data on consumption from FAO food balance sheets (FBS) FAO (2014). Three geodatasets (GIS-rasters) for the green, blue and grey $WF_{prod, agr}$ for crops ($WF_{prod, agr-crops}$) (Mekonnen and Hoekstra 2011a, Mekonnen and Hoekstra 2010) with a 5 arc minute spatial resolution were obtained from the Water Footprint Network. These geodatasets are calculated based upon the crop growing areas (on a 5 by 5 arc minute grid cell resolution) from Monfreda *et al* (2008) and Portmann *et al* (2010). These geodatasets also comprise the crops which are used as feed. National blue (service water) and green (grazing) $WF_{prod, agr}$ data for livestock ($WF_{prod, agr-liv}$) were obtained from Mekonnen and Hoekstra (2012) and Mekonnen and Hoekstra (2011b). The period for which the analyses were made is 1996–2005. This period is identified as REF within this study.

2.4. River basin WF and VW values

The methodology to compute river basin values based upon raster values (for the green, blue and grey $WF_{prod, agr-crops}$) and national values (for the green, blue and grey $WF_{prod, agr-liv}$ and $WF_{cons, agr}$) is presented in figure 2. The application of this methodology is presented in online supplementary figure A.1, available at stacks.iop.org/ERL/00/000000/mmedia for green water and in figure A.2 for blue water. To assess a green and blue $WF_{prod, agr-liv}$ raster, national $WF_{prod, agr-liv}$ data for grazing and livestock service water were extrapolated by means of the gridded livestock of the world (GLW) rasters (with a 1 km spatial resolution (year 2000)) for different livestock types FAO (2013). The group horses, donkeys and mules is not represented by a GLW raster. To spatially distribute this livestock type, national stock data FAO (2014) are interpolated by means of the cattle GLW raster. Raster geodata of the green, blue and grey $WF_{cons, agr}$ are obtained by multiplying national $WF_{cons, agr}$ values (Hoekstra and Mekonnen 2012a, Mekonnen and Hoekstra 2011b) with the population raster of CIESIN (2005).

Figure 3 Map of European countries where the basins are (partly) located in, with indication of applicable regional Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDG) for HEALTHY.

2.5. Diets

In this study three diets—the current diet (REF, 1996–2005), a healthy diet (HEALTHY) based on regional FBDG (table A.1 and figure 3) and a VEG are assessed. A detailed description on the methodology how to analyse the $WF_{cons, agr}$ for HEALTHY and VEG can be found in Vanham *et al* (2013a). In Vanham *et al* (2013a), three regional FBDG were used for the EU28: (1) the recommendations of the German nutrition society (DGE—Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ernährung, Elmadfa *et al* 2009, WHO 2003), (2) the recommendations for a Mediterranean diet (MED) based upon Willett *et al* (1995), Bach-Faig *et al* (2011) and Aranceta and Serra-Majem (2001), (3) the recommendations of Scandinavian countries for northern Europe (NORTH) (Barbieri and Lindvall 2005, Astrup *et al* 2005). Figure 3 shows which HEALTHY FBDG were used for which countries. In this paper, an additional FBDG for HEALTHY for Turkey (The Ministry of Health of Turkey 2006) was used. An overview on the four FBDG is given in table A.1, as taken from Vanham *et al* (2013a) and adapted with FBDG from the Ministry of Health of Turkey (2006).

In this paper, a diet scenario analysis and its effect on the $WF_{cons, agr}$ is conducted for each of the 40 nations separately based upon regional FBDG (figure 3). This assessment is much more detailed than in Vanham *et al* (2013a), where such an analysis was only done for four aggregated EU zones. The amounts of fish recommended by the respective FBDG are substituted by meat. The reason for this is that no WF data for fish have been published thus far. Like in Vanham *et al* (2013a), a VEG includes the intake of milk and milk products

(cheese, butter, yoghurt, etc). All meat is substituted by the group pulses, nuts and oilcrops, by an increase in the intake of pulses and soybeans. National data on food consumption (period 1996–2005)—on which basis the WF_{cons} is calculated—were taken from the FAO FBS (FAO 2014).

3. Results

3.1. $WF_{prod, agr}$, $WF_{cons, agr}$ and $netVW_{i, agr}$ for the REF

The results for 22 major river basins in table form are presented in table A.2 ($WF_{prod, agr}$), table A.3 ($WF_{cons, agr}$) and table A.4 ($netVW_{i, agr}$).

Figure 4 shows that river basins where the $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ exceeds the $WF_{prod, agr, tot}$ substantially (resulting in positive $netVW_{i, agr, tot}$ values), are found along the densely populated and heavily industrialized London–Milan axis. Major river basins include the Thames ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 130\,363\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 1025\,948\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = 895\,585\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$), Scheldt ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 200\,524\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 704\,998\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = 504\,474\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$), Rhine ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 109\,720\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 369\,261\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = 259\,541\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$) and Po basins ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 219\,630\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 465\,324\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = 245\,694\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$). Other such basins include the Tajo basin (which encompasses the city of Madrid) or small urban river basins like the Besòs river basin in which a large part of the city of Barcelona is located.

Large river basins where the $WF_{prod, agr, tot}$ exceeds the $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ (resulting in negative $netVW_{i, agr, tot}$ values) are found in Western France, the Iberian Peninsula and the Baltic region. These include the Loire ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 153\,663\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 104\,632\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = -49\,031\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$), Ebro ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 170\,756\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 76\,412\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = -94\,344\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$) and Nemunas basins ($WF_{prod, agr, tot} = 140\,047\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot} = 75\,291\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $netVW_{i, agr, tot} = -64\,757\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$). They are characterized by low population densities and are important agricultural production regions.

Generally the same observations are made for assessments when excluding the grey WF component (figure 4, bottom row). Figure A.3 shows that similar observations are made when only the green or grey WF components are assessed. When only the blue WF component is assessed, a different pattern is observed for the river basins. High $WF_{prod, agr, bl}$ values are concentrated in the Mediterranean region due to irrigated agriculture and to a lesser extent in the Benelux region due to livestock service water. Examples are the Guadalquivir ($WF_{prod, agr-crops, bl} = 74\,058\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr-liv, bl} = 980\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr, bl} = 75\,037\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$), Ebro ($WF_{prod, agr-crops, bl} = 22\,799\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr-liv, bl} = 2341\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr, bl} = 25\,140\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$) or Scheldt basins ($WF_{prod, agr-crops, bl} = 1580\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr-liv, bl} = 7597\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$, $WF_{prod, agr, bl} = 9177\text{ m}^3\text{ km}^{-2}$). These products are consumed throughout Europe. As a result, blue

Figure 4 $WF_{prod, agr, tot}$, $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ and $netVW_{i, agr, tot}$ (above) and $WF_{prod, agr, gn+bl}$, $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$ and $netVW_{i, agr, gn+bl}$ (below) for the reference period (REF, 1996–2005) for the assessed river basins (all in $m^3 km^{-2}$).

net VW export basins (negative $netVW_{i, agr, bl}$ values) are concentrated in the Mediterranean, whereas other basins are predominately blue net VW import basins (positive $netVW_{i, agr, bl}$ values).

3.2. $WF_{cons, agr}$ for the diet scenarios

Table 2 shows national $WF_{cons, agr}$ values for different diet scenarios (REF, HEALTHY and VEG), as a result of separate national analyses. To date, such an analysis was only available for Austria (Vanham 2013b). Transposed to river basins, the effect of HEALTHY and VEG on the $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ and $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$ is shown in figure 5. For HEALTHY, the $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ of most river basins decreases (maximum -31.9%), although in eastern and northern Europe some basins show an increase (similar for $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$). High

decreases are e.g. observed in large basins like the Loire (-30.5%) or Po basin (-31.7%). The increase in some eastern and northern basins is for some basins the result of high meat intake recommendations in the FBDG of NORTH (basins in e.g. the Balkan countries, Finland and Norway). Within other basins this is the result of a general under-nutrition of products like crop oils, fruit, eggs, pulses and nuts, and for some milk and meat (basins in e.g. upper middle income countries like Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia and lower middle income countries like Ukraine).

For VEG, in all but one river basin a reduction (maximum -46.4%) is observed. High reductions are observed in e.g. the Loire (-46.4%), Rhone (-44.6%), Scheldt (-44.6%) or Po basins (-44.3%). Similar observations are made for the $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$.

Table 2 National $WF_{cons, agr}$ values for different diets (REF, HEALTHY and VEG) (in lcd).

Country	REF				HEALTHY				VEG			
	green	blue	grey	total	green	blue	grey	Total (with % difference)	green	blue	grey	Total (with % difference)
Albania	3000	456	208	3663	3239	472	236	3947 (+8%)	2487	387	215	3090 (-16%)
Austria	3108	181	366	3655	2309	157	267	2733 (-25%)	1931	142	220	2293 (-37%)
Belarus	3581	123	575	4279	3429	124	692	4245 (-1%)	2717	96	669	3482 (-19%)
Belgium	3331	254	294	3879	2386	202	222	2810 (-28%)	1822	176	186	2184 (-44%)
Bosnia-Herzegovina	2924	79	263	3267	3834	99	365	4298 (+32%)	3107	80	323	3511 (+8%)
Bulgaria	4957	145	395	5497	5417	161	454	6032 (+10%)	4040	133	388	4561 (-17%)
Cyprus	4609	897	341	5846	3671	958	324	4953 (-15%)	2948	1040	320	4308 (-26%)
Croatia	3712	80	509	4301	3655	82	505	4242 (-1%)	2903	65	399	3366 (-22%)
Czech Republic	3388	157	520	4065	2761	158	415	3335 (-18%)	2190	142	335	2667 (-34%)
Denmark	3348	192	368	3908	2789	162	314	3264 (-17%)	2028	124	241	2393 (-39%)
Estonia	3601	381	309	4292	3935	386	328	4649 (+8%)	2882	351	247	3479 (-19%)
Finland	2896	135	158	3189	2920	153	166	3239 (+1.6%)	2075	122	142	2339 (-27%)
France	3708	274	269	4251	2546	217	193	2956 (-30%)	1930	182	166	2277 (-46%)
Germany	2886	159	406	3450	2200	138	315	2652 (-23%)	1784	117	249	2150 (-38%)
Greece	4526	828	455	5810	3074	601	321	3996 (-31%)	2473	537	280	3290 (-43%)
Hungary	5250	115	615	5980	4341	114	532	4987 (-17%)	3546	104	487	4136 (-31%)
Ireland	2574	249	283	3106	2130	220	235	2585 (-17%)	1504	172	201	1876 (-40%)
Italy	4714	441	484	5639	3196	321	323	3839 (-32%)	2592	280	260	3131 (-45%)
Latvia	3634	109	361	4104	4501	140	448	5089 (+24%)	2830	116	289	3236 (-21%)
Lithuania	3470	108	153	3732	3858	130	160	4149 (+11%)	2703	95	124	2922 (-22%)
Luxembourg*	3328	131	451	3910	2253	98	295	2645 (-32%)	1856	83	282	2220 (-43%)
Macedonia	2698	203	200	3101	3044	229	222	3495 (+13%)	2431	197	189	2817 (-9%)
Malta	4589	510	375	5474	3323	402	295	4019 (-27%)	2516	326	255	3098 (-43%)
Moldova	2846	283	94	3223	3835	411	108	4354 (+35%)	3050	350	91	3491 (+8%)
Netherlands	2893	280	275	3448	2142	207	223	2572 (-25%)	1754	182	205	2140 (-38%)
Norway	2804	246	186	3236	2925	223	194	3343 (+3%)	1943	186	194	2323 (-28%)
Poland	2769	104	481	3353	2347	100	356	2802 (-16%)	1990	77	293	2360 (-30%)
Portugal	5080	943	429	6452	3958	729	307	4994 (-23%)	3481	617	257	4355 (-32%)
Romania	3684	161	209	4054	3526	154	193	3873 (-5%)	2852	122	209	3182 (-22%)
Russia	4244	224	165	4632	4299	263	160	4722 (+2%)	3091	213	133	3438 (-26%)
Serbia and Montenegro: Serbia	3649	100	299	4048	3570	104	307	3982 (-4%)	2933	83	336	3352 (-19%)
Serbia and Montenegro: Montenegro	3649	100	299	4048	3267	84	316	3668 (-9%)	2774	68	346	3188 (-21%)
Slovakia	2779	152	297	3228	2760	177	293	3230 (+0.1%)	2274	152	241	2667 (-17%)
Slovenia	3687	182	819	4687	2995	163	729	3888 (-17%)	2630	148	735	3513 (-25%)
Spain	4937	805	576	6318	3418	588	422	4428 (-30%)	2947	516	375	3838 (-39%)
Sweden	2844	144	382	3370	2736	160	374	3270 (-3%)	1819	127	252	2198 (-35%)
Switzerland	2836	216	350	3402	2268	185	304	2757 (-19%)	1875	162	281	2318 (-32%)
Turkey	3150	655	331	4136	2718	612	289	3619 (-13%)	2228	585	272	3085 (-25%)
UK	2508	199	313	3021	2426	208	311	2946 (-3%)	1644	172	235	2051 (-32%)
Ukraine	3215	98	182	3495	3638	121	238	3997 (+14%)	2779	85	220	3084 (-12%)

Note: (*)for Luxembourg rubber is substituted by the EU-average

Figure A.4 shows generally the same observations for the green and blue WF components. For HEALTHY, the decrease/increase in $WF_{cons, agr, gn}$ ranges between -32.2% and 23.9% (288 basins decrease, 77 increase) and in $WF_{cons, agr, bl}$ between -27.4% and 37.7% (212 basins decrease, 153 increase). For VEG, the decrease/increase in $WF_{cons, agr, gn}$ ranges between -48.0% and 0.2% (364 basins decrease, 1 increase) and in $WF_{cons, agr, bl}$ between -36.5% and 16.0% (358 basins decrease, 7 increase).

3.3. Net $VW_{i, agr}$ for the diet scenarios

The changes in $WF_{cons, agr}$ for the diet scenarios also lead to changes in the net $VW_{i, agr}$ of river basins. Figure 6 shows these changes for net $VW_{i, agr, tot}$ and net $VW_{i, agr, gn+bl}$. For the net $VW_{i, agr, tot}$ HEALTHY results in a shift from net VW_i to net VW_e for 22 of 365 river basins, amongst which the Danube basin (from 2243 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to -9387 $m^3 km^{-2}$) (table A.4). Two small basins shift from net VW_e to net VW_i . VEG results in a shift from net VW_i to net VW_e for 50 river basins,

Figure 5 Percentage reduction in $WF_{cons, agr, tot}$ (above) and $WF_{cons, agr, gn+bl}$ (below) within the river basins due to different diets (left HEALTHY; right VEG).

amongst which large basins like the Danube (from 2,243 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-35\,331 m^3 km^{-2}$), Seine (from 111 225 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-36,746 m^3 km^{-2}$), Rhone (from 66 148 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-2585 m^3 km^{-2}$) and Elbe basins (from 57 855 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-23\,410 m^3 km^{-2}$). For the $netVW_{i, agr, gn+bl}$, generally the same observations are made.

When only the green and blue WF components are assessed (figure A.5), the shifts in $netVW_{i, agr, gn}$ are

predominantly similar as shown in figure 6. For the $netVW_{i, agr, bl}$, most basins remain $netVW_i$ for HEALTHY (262 basins) and VEG (244 basins). For HEALTHY, 15 basins shift from $netVW_i$ to $netVW_e$, amongst which the Loire basin (from 150 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-1253 m^3 km^{-2}$). For VEG, 33 basins shift from $netVW_i$ to $netVW_e$, of which the largest the Loire (from 150 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-2115 m^3 km^{-2}$) and the Tajo basins (from 9965 $m^3 km^{-2}$ to $-746 m^3 km^{-2}$).

Figure 6 Shift in netVW_{i, agr, tot}/netVW_{e, agr, tot} (above) and netVW_{i, agr, gn+bl}/netVW_{e, agr, gn+bl} (below) within the river basins due to different diets (left HEALTHY; right VEG).

4. Discussion

4.1. General

This paper shows that there are substantial differences in the amounts and characterizations of the current (REF) WF_{prod, agr}, WF_{cons, agr} and resulting netVW_{i, agr} in European river basins. The diet scenarios show substantial shifts in the

WF_{cons, agr}, with resulting shifts in net VW_{i, agr} amounts. From the perspective of FBDG, the WF_{cons, agr} for both the HEALTHY and VEG scenarios can be regarded as being sustainable. From the water use perspective, the WF_{cons, agr} can be regarded as being more sustainable under the VEG than under the HEALTHY scenario. Not assessed in this paper is the preferred consumption of local and seasonal food,

which can have some additional effect on the quantity and composition (green, blue, grey) of the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$.

As a next step, the sustainability of the current river basin $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$ should be assessed, with the relevant blue, green and grey WF sustainability indicators (Vanham and Bidoglio 2013a, Hoekstra *et al* 2011). Already today several of the analysed river basins experience (blue) water stress (Hoekstra *et al* 2012). The maximum sustainable $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$ should be addressed per river basin. This can mean that the reference $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$ of some river basins will have to be reduced while that of others can still be increased. Different pathways to achieving such an outcome are available. Sustainable agricultural intensification is identified as the way forward by different authors (Foley *et al* 2011, Godfray *et al* 2010, Tilman *et al* 2011). Yield gaps need to be closed on underperforming lands, while also reducing the environmental impacts of agriculture. If such a maximum sustainable $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$ as well as the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ of a HEALTHY and/or VEG diet were to be implemented, it is anticipated that a sustainable situation from a water resources point of view is reached. Additionally other resources/indicators such as land use and GHG emissions need to be assessed. Only by evaluating different indicators, integrated policy options can be defined.

4.2. Uncertainty in data and methodology

Different assumptions and simplifications were made in this study. Due to data availability restrictions, the results of this assessment are not absolute and must be regarded as best estimates based upon direct underlying data on production (for the $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$) and consumption (for the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$). Both can be calculated by means of the top-down or bottom-up approach (Hoekstra *et al* 2011). In this Letter, both are calculated with the bottom-up which is based upon direct underlying data on production and consumption—FAOSTAT data (FAO 2014)—and is less sensitive to trade data than the top-down approach (Hoekstra and Mekonnen 2012). As described in Vanham and Bidoglio (2013b), the balance $WF_{\text{prod}} + VW_i = WF_{\text{cons}} + VW_e$ within the geographic WF accounting scheme as calculated for the EU with the bottom-up approach does not hold 100%. For the EU28, for agricultural products, these values are 552 km^3 ($WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$), 360 km^3 ($VW_{i, \text{ agr}}$), 759 km^3 ($WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$) and 95 km^3 ($VW_{e, \text{ agr}}$) (Vanham and Bidoglio, 2013b). The balance therefore shifts between 855 and 912 km^3 (range of about 6%). Theoretically this balance should close. This is however not the case due to practical complexities with data (availability of and inconsistencies in the underlying databases). As such the results of this assessment need to be regarded as best estimates.

The assumptions related to the methodology used to compute river basin values (figure 2, figure A.2 and figure A.3) were discussed in detail in Vanham (2013a). An important assumption is the fact that the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ raster is obtained by spatially disaggregating national $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ data by means of a population raster dataset. This assumes that the consumption pattern is homogenous within each country.

This is in reality not the case and thus a simplification. To account for this heterogeneity, regional statistics within a country could be used. Such detailed consumption data are however currently lacking (Hoff *et al* 2014, Vanham and Bidoglio 2014).

The grey WF methodology needs to be further standardized (Vanham and Bidoglio 2013a), therefore $WF_{\text{prod, agr, tot}}$ and $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ results were additionally shown without the grey component ($WF_{\text{prod, agr, gn+bl}}$ and $WF_{\text{cons, agr, gn+bl}}$).

Methodology assumptions and data availability for computing the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ of the different diet scenarios were discussed in detail in Vanham *et al* (2013a). For the diets of the different zones e.g., average values were chosen from selected FBDG (table A.1), although recommendations for specific product groups often indicate a range of intake. Correction factors to compute intake values from consumption data are based upon a list of publications but are not available on a zonal/regional level (Vanham *et al* 2013a). An important issue is also that, although regional FBDG include fish, WF values for fish (and seafood) have not yet been published. In our analyses, these recommended amounts were substituted by meat. The $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ for the HEALTHY and VEG diets thus include the protein and energy intake of fish (substituted by meat), but the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ calculated under the REF diet scenario does not represent the current intake of fish (and seafood) at all.

Figure A.6 shows the REF and recommended intake values of meat (including offals) and fish (including seafood) for the 40 countries. Indeed, substantial fish (including seafood) amounts are part of the REF diet in all zones. By not incorporating these values, the current $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ is in fact underestimated. Especially for different countries in the FBDG zone NORTH (Finland, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden), the recommended intake of meat including fish (49.3 kg per cap per year) is exceeded when including, but not reached when excluding, the latter. This explains higher HEALTHY $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ values as compared to (underestimated) REF $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ values.

Figure A.7 shows that during the past decades the intake of meat (including offals) and fish (including seafood) has evolved to some extent. As compared to REF (1996–2005), countries with very high intakes (France, Spain) have decreased their intake whereas many with low intake values show a steady increase.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a comprehensive quantification and analysis of the $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$, the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ and the resulting $netVW_{i, \text{ agr}}$ for 365 EU river basins for a REF (1996–2005) and two diet scenarios (HEALTHY and VEG). The analysis differentiates between the different green, blue and grey WF components. Such a comprehensive analysis on the river basin scale is the first in its kind.

Substantial differences in amounts and characterizations of the river basins' REF $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$, $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ and resulting $netVW_{i, \text{ agr}}$ are observed. The highly industrialized and

densely populated river basins along the London–Milan axis show higher $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ than $WF_{\text{prod, agr}}$ amounts (for tot, gn + bl and gn), identifying them as net VW importer basins. These include major basins such as the Thames, Scheldt, Meuse, Seine, Rhine and Po basins. River basins where the $WF_{\text{prod, agr, tot}}$ exceeds $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ amounts (net VW exporter basins) (for tot, gn + bl and gn) are found in western France (Loire, Garonne), the Iberian Peninsula (Ebro, Duero, Guadiana, Guadalquivir) and the greater Baltic region (Nemunas). These basins are sparsely populated with extensive agricultural areas. A different pattern is observed for the river basins when only the blue WF component is analysed. High $WF_{\text{prod, agr, bl}}$ values are concentrated in the Mediterranean region (Guadalquivir, Ebro) due to irrigated agriculture and to a lesser extent in the Benelux region (Scheldt) due to livestock service water. Blue net VW exporter basins are concentrated in the Mediterranean.

The different diet scenarios lead to substantial shifts in the $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ with resulting shifts in net $VW_{i, agr}$ amounts. For the HEALTHY scenario, the $WF_{\text{cons, agr, tot}}$ of most river basins decreases with exceptions in northern and eastern Europe. High decreases are observed in e.g. the Loire (−30.5%) and Po (−31.7%) basins. As a result, 22 of the 365 river basins shift from being net VW importers to being net VW exporters. For the VEG scenario, a reduction is observed in 364 of 365 basins. High reductions are observed in e.g. the Loire (−46.4%), Rhone (−44.6%), Scheldt (−44.6%) or Po (−44.3%) basins. This results in a shift of 50 river basins from being net VW importers to being net VW exporters. Similar observations are made for the $WF_{\text{cons, agr, gn+bl}}$ (and net $VW_{\text{agr, gn+bl}}$) and for the $WF_{\text{cons, agr, gn}}$ (and net $VW_{\text{agr, gn}}$). With regard to the blue WF component, 15 basins (including the Loire) shift from being net VW importers to being net VW exporters under the HEALTHY scenario –and 33 basins (including the Loire and Tajo) under the VEG scenario.

Such reduced river basin $WF_{\text{cons, agr}}$ can contribute to sustainable water management both within the EU and beyond its borders. They could help to reduce the dependency of EU consumption on domestic and foreign water resources or even increase virtual water exports from the EU to other regions, thereby contributing to the mitigation of the growing water scarcity in other parts of the world (Vanham *et al* 2013b). As global land and water resources are finite, adaptations in both production and consumption need to be made.

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References

- Aldaya M M and Llamas M R 2009 Water footprint analysis (hydrologic and economic) of the Guadiana river basin (*Scientific Side paper Series from WWDR-3*) (UNESCO)
- Aranceta J and Serra-Majem L 2001 Dietary guidelines for the Spanish population *Public Health Nutrition* **4** 1403–8
- Astrup A, Andersen N L, Stender S and Trolle E 2005 Kostrådene 2005 Copenhagen, Ernaeringsrådet og Danmarks Fødevareforskning
- Bach-Faig A *et al* 2011 Mediterranean diet pyramid today. science and cultural updates *Public Health Nutrition* **14** 2274–84
- Barbieri H E and Lindvall C 2005 *Swedish Nutrition Recommendations Objectified (SNO)* (Uppsala, Sweden: National Food Administration)
- CIESIN 2005 *Gridded Population of the World Version 3 (GPWv3)* (Palisades, NY: Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC))
- Dumont A, Salmoral G and Llamas M R 2013 The water footprint of a river basin with a special focus on groundwater: the case of Guadalquivir basin (Spain) *Water Resour. Ind.* **1–2** 60–76
- EC 2012 *River Basin Management Plans—REPORT on the Implementation of the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)* (Brussels: European Commission)
- Elmadfa I *et al* 2009 *European Nutrition and Health Report 2009* (Basel: Forum of Nutrition)
- FAO 2013 *Gridded Livestock of the World (GLW)* (Rome: FAO)
- FAO 2014 *FAOSTAT On-Line Database* (Rome: FAO)
- Foley J A *et al* 2011 Solutions for a cultivated planet *Nature* **478** 337–42
- Galli A, Wiedmann T, Ercin E, Knoblauch D, Ewing B and Giljum S 2012 Integrating ecological, carbon and water footprint into a ‘footprint family’ of indicators: definition and role in tracking human pressure on the planet *Ecol. Indica* **16** 100–12
- Godfray H C J, Beddington J R, Crute I R, Haddad L, Lawrence D, Muir J F, Pretty J, Robinson S, Thomas S M and Toulmin C 2010 Food security: the challenge of feeding 9 billion people *Science* **327** 812–8
- Hoekstra A Y, Chapagain A K, Aldaya M M and Mekonnen M M 2011 *The Water Footprint Assessment Manual: Setting the Global Standard* (London, UK: Earthscan)
- Hoekstra A Y and Mekonnen M M 2012 The water footprint of humanity *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **109** 3232–7
- Hoekstra A Y, Mekonnen M M, Chapagain A K, Mathews R E and Richter B D 2012 Global monthly water scarcity: blue water footprints versus blue water availability *PLoS ONE* **7** e32688
- Hoff H, Döll P, Fader M, Gerten D, Hauser S and Siebert S 2014 Water footprints of cities — indicators for sustainable consumption and production *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* **18** 213–26
- Liu J and Savenije H H G 2008 Food consumption patterns and their effect on water requirement in China *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* **12** 887–98
- Mekonnen M and Hoekstra A 2012 A global assessment of the water footprint of farm animal products *Ecosystems* **15** 401–15
- Mekonnen M M and Hoekstra A Y 2010 *The Green, Blue and Grey Water Footprint of Crops and Derived Crop Products* (Delft: UNESCO-IHE Institute for Water Education)
- Mekonnen M M and Hoekstra A Y 2011a The green, blue and grey water footprint of crops and derived crop products *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* **15** 1577–600
- Mekonnen M M and Hoekstra A Y 2011b *National Water Footprint Accounts: The Green, Blue and Grey Water Footprint of Production and Consumption* (Delft: UNESCO-IHE Institute for Water Education)
- Monfreda C, Ramankutty N and Foley J A 2008 Farming the planet: 2. geographic distribution of crop areas, yields, physiological

- types, and net primary production in the year 2000 *Glob. Biogeochem. Cy.* **22** GB1022
- Portmann F T, Siebert S and Döll P 2010 Mirca2000—global monthly irrigated and rainfed crop areas around the year 2000: A new high-resolution data set for agricultural and hydrological modelling *Glob. Biogeochem. Cy.* **24** GB1011
- Rockström J, Falkenmark M, Karlberg L, Hoff H, Rost S and Gerten D 2009 Future water availability for global food production: the potential of green water for increasing resilience to global change *Water Resour. Res.* **45** W00A12
- The Ministry of Health of Turkey 2006 *Dietary Guidelines for Turkey* (Ankara, Turkey: The Ministry of Health of Turkey)
- Tilman D, Balzer C, Hill J and Befort B L 2011 Global food demand and the sustainable intensification of agriculture *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **108** 20260–4
- Vanham D 2013a An assessment of the virtual water balance for agricultural products in EU river basins *Water Resour. Ind.* **1-2** 49–59
- Vanham D 2013b The water footprint of Austria for different diets *Water Sci. Technol.* **67** 824–30
- Vanham D and Bidoglio G 2013a A review on the indicator water footprint for the EU28 *Ecol. Indicators* **26** 61–75
- Vanham D and Bidoglio G 2013b A review on the indicator water footprint for the EU28 *Ecol. Indicators* **26** 61–75
- Vanham D and Bidoglio G 2014 The water footprint of Milan *Water Sci. Technol.* **69** 789–95
- Vanham D, Hoekstra A Y and Bidoglio G 2013a Potential water saving through changes in European diets *Environ. Int.* **61** 45–56
- Vanham D, Mekonnen M M and Hoekstra A Y 2013b The water footprint of the EU for different diets *Ecol. Indic.* **32** 1–8
- Vogt J *et al* 2007 *A Pan-European River and Catchment Database* (Luxembourg: IN JRC)
- WHO 2003 *Food Based Dietary Guidelines in the WHO European Region* (Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe)
- Willett W C, Sacks F, Trichopoulos A, Drescher G, Ferro-Luzzi A, Helsing E and Trichopoulos D 1995 Mediterranean diet pyramid: a cultural model for healthy eating *Am. J. Clin. Nutrition* **61** 1402s–6s
- Zeng Z, Liu J, Koeneman P H, Zarate E and Hoekstra A Y 2012 Assessing water footprint at river basin level: a case study for the heihe river basin in northwest China *Hydrol. Earth. Syst. Sci.* **16** 2771–81
- Zhao X, Yang H, Yang Z, Chen B and Qin Y 2010 Applying the input-output method to account for water footprint and virtual water trade in the haihe river basin in China *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **44** 9150–6